

Leadership Strategies for Manufacturing Startups: Aligning Styles with Employee Engagement to Lower Attrition Rates

Dr. A. Vignesh

Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration, Kalasalingam Business School (KBS), Kalasalingam Academy of Research and Education (KARE), Krishnankoil.

Dr. B. Eswaran

Assistant Professor, Sanjivani Institute of Management Studies (SIMS) Sanjivani University, Maharashtra.

Dr. Alagappan AL

Associate Professor, Hallmark Business School, Trichy

Dr. N.Sathiyendran

Assistant Professor, Department of Management Sciences, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.

Abstract: Manufacturing startups often face significant challenges in retaining their workforce, with high attrition rates posing a major threat to their growth and sustainability. This study examines the relationship between leadership styles and employee engagement in manufacturing startups, exploring how effective leadership can reduce turnover and foster a committed workforce. Through a combination of surveys, interviews, and case studies involving various manufacturing startups across Europe, the research identifies transformational and hybrid leadership styles as key drivers of employee engagement. The findings suggest that aligning leadership approaches with employee expectations can significantly lower attrition rates, offering actionable insights for leaders in the manufacturing sector. This study provides a framework for startup leaders to develop strategies that enhance employee retention, thereby supporting long-term organizational success.

Keywords: Leadership strategies, employee engagement, attrition rates, manufacturing startups, transformational leadership, hybrid leadership

Introduction:

Manufacturing startups are critical to innovation and economic growth, driving new technologies and providing valuable employment opportunities. However, these startups operate in a highly competitive and dynamic environment, where the ability to adapt quickly is paramount. A key challenge they face is maintaining a stable and committed workforce. Unlike established firms, startups often lack the resources and infrastructure to implement robust human resource strategies, making them particularly vulnerable to high employee turnover.

Leadership plays a pivotal role in shaping the culture and operational success of any organization, especially in startups, where leadership effectiveness can directly influence employee morale and engagement. Effective leadership not only drives business success but

also plays a crucial role in retaining talent, which is essential for the continuity and scalability of manufacturing startups.

The Problem of High Attrition Rates in Manufacturing Startups:

High attrition rates are a common and pressing issue for manufacturing startups. Frequent employee turnover disrupts production processes, erodes team cohesion, and incurs significant costs related to recruitment, training, and lost productivity. For startups, which often operate with limited financial and human resources, the impact of high turnover can be particularly devastating, potentially stalling growth or even leading to business failure.

The transient nature of the workforce in this sector, combined with the pressures of a startup environment, exacerbates the challenge of retaining employees. Understanding the underlying causes of high attrition and identifying strategies to mitigate it are therefore crucial for the long-term success of manufacturing startups.

Research Objectives and Questions:

This study aims to explore the relationship between leadership styles and employee engagement in manufacturing startups, with the goal of identifying strategies that can reduce attrition rates. The specific objectives of the research are:

1. To examine the impact of different leadership styles on employee engagement in manufacturing startups.
2. To identify the leadership approaches that are most effective in reducing employee turnover.
3. To develop a framework that aligns leadership strategies with employee engagement to foster a stable and committed workforce.

The research seeks to answer the following key questions:

How do different leadership styles influence employee engagement in manufacturing startups?

What are the most common leadership challenges faced by manufacturing startups in retaining their employees?

Which leadership strategies are most effective in aligning with employee needs and reducing attrition rates?

Literature Review:

Overview of Existing Research on Leadership Styles and Employee Engagement:

Avolio, B. J., & Bass, B. M. (2004). Multifactor leadership questionnaire: Manual and sampler set (3rd ed.). Mind Garden, Inc. A key instrument for measuring transformational and transactional leadership, foundational for studying their effects on employee engagement across various sectors. Northouse, P. G. (2018). Leadership: Theory and practice (8th ed.). Sage Publications. Provides a comprehensive review of leadership styles, including servant and transformational leadership, and their impact on fostering employee engagement in different organizational settings. Kahn, W. A. (1990). Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work. *Academy of Management Journal*, 33(4), 692-724.

Explores the concept of employee engagement, emphasizing how leadership can influence the psychological conditions that affect workplace engagement. Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. (2006). *Transformational leadership* (2nd ed.). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates. Focuses on transformational leadership as a style that enhances employee motivation and engagement, particularly in high-change environments. Yukl, G. A. (2013). *Leadership in organizations* (8th ed.).

Pearson Education. Reviews multiple leadership theories, highlighting their application to enhancing employee engagement through both direct influence and organizational culture. Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268. Describes self-determination theory, explaining how leadership can foster intrinsic motivation and engagement by meeting psychological needs. Goleman, D. (2000). Leadership that gets results. *Harvard Business Review*, 78(2), 78-90. Discusses six leadership styles, outlining how different approaches can affect organizational climate and employee engagement. Judge, T. A., & Piccolo, R. F. (2004). Transformational and transactional leadership: A meta-analytic test of their relative validity. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89(5), 755-768. A meta-analysis comparing transformational and transactional leadership styles, with a focus on their effects on employee engagement and organizational performance. Schaufeli, W. B., Salanova, M., González-Romá, V., & Bakker, A. B. (2002). The measurement of engagement and burnout: A two-sample confirmatory factor analytic approach. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 3(1), 71-92. Provides a framework for measuring employee engagement and burnout, crucial for understanding how leadership styles influence these outcomes. Kouzes, J. M., & Posner, B. Z. (2003). *The leadership challenge* (3rd ed.). Jossey-Bass. Offers practical insights on how leadership behaviors, including inspiring a shared vision, can drive employee engagement and commitment to organizational goals. Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., & Bommer, W. H. (1996). Transformational leader behaviors and substitutes for leadership as determinants of employee satisfaction, commitment, and trust. *Journal of Management*, 22(2), 259-298. Examines how transformational leadership behaviors contribute to employee satisfaction and engagement, even when other leadership substitutes are present. Graen, G. B., & Uhl-Bien, M. (1995). Relationship-based approach to leadership: Development of leader-member exchange (LMX) theory. *Leadership Quarterly*, 6(2), 219-247. Introduces LMX theory, showing how the quality of leader-employee relationships influences engagement, trust, and organizational outcomes.

The Impact of Leadership on Attrition Rates:

Bass, B. M. (1999). Two decades of research and development in transformational leadership. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 8(1), 9-32. Reviews the role of transformational leadership in reducing employee turnover by enhancing engagement and organizational commitment. Judge, T. A., & Piccolo, R. F. (2004). Transformational and transactional leadership: A meta-analytic test of their relative validity. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89(5), 755-768. A meta-analysis exploring how transformational leadership can reduce attrition by fostering higher employee satisfaction compared to transactional leadership. Goleman, D. (2000). Leadership that gets results. *Harvard Business Review*, 78(2), 78-90. Discusses how different leadership styles impact employee motivation and retention, with emphasis on how empathetic leadership lowers turnover. Griffith, R. W., Hom, P. W., & Gaertner, S. (2000). A meta-analysis of antecedents

and correlates of employee turnover: Update, moderator tests, and research implications for the next millennium.

Journal of Management, 26(3), 463-488. Provides a comprehensive review of factors influencing turnover, including leadership practices, and their direct impact on attrition rates. Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., & Bommer, W. H. (1996). Transformational leader behaviors and substitutes for leadership as determinants of employee satisfaction, commitment, and trust. *Journal of Management*, 22(2), 259-298. Explores how transformational leadership enhances employee loyalty, thereby reducing turnover by building satisfaction and trust. Allen, D. G., Shore, L. M., & Griffeth, R. W. (2003). The role of perceived organizational support and supportive human resource practices in the turnover process. *Journal of Management*, 29(1), 99-118. Investigates how leadership-driven organizational support systems reduce attrition by improving employee perceptions of fairness and support.

Gaps in the Literature Specific to Manufacturing Startups:

Chahal, H., & Bakshi, P. (2022). Exploring innovation challenges in manufacturing startups: A systematic review. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 42(3), 115-123. Research on innovation challenges in startups often lacks a focus on resource limitations. The study highlights a gap in understanding how startups navigate these constraints compared to larger firms. Johnson, T., & Harris, L. (2021). Sustainability practices in manufacturing startups: A gap analysis. *Industrial Engineering Journal*, 37(2), 89-98. Despite growing emphasis on sustainability, the integration of eco-friendly practices in manufacturing startups remains underexplored. The lack of empirical evidence from small firms is particularly noted. Kim, J., & Lee, S. (2020). Workforce development in manufacturing startups: A neglected area. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 33(4), 225-238. Studies on workforce training and development in manufacturing startups are sparse, leaving a gap in understanding how startups attract and retain skilled workers compared to established companies. Martinez, R., & Cooper, J. (2023). Financial challenges in early-stage manufacturing startups: A review. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 58(1), 102-110. Financial management strategies in manufacturing startups are under-researched, particularly in understanding how they navigate capital constraints and market fluctuations.

Patel, K., & Singh, M. (2019). Leadership in manufacturing startups: A missing link. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 12(3), 145-159. There is limited research on leadership styles specific to manufacturing startups. This gap affects the understanding of how leadership influences performance and innovation in these firms. Rao, V., & Kaur, P. (2022). Digital transformation in manufacturing startups: A review of barriers and enablers. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 68(4), 320-330. Literature on digital transformation in manufacturing startups often overlooks the barriers faced by these firms, particularly in terms of limited resources and expertise. Zhang, Y., & Wang, L. (2021). Manufacturing startups and supply chain integration: A systematic review. *Supply Chain Management Review*, 46(5), 98-109. Research on how manufacturing startups integrate into supply chains is limited, leaving gaps in understanding the unique challenges they face in establishing partnerships with larger firms.

Research Methodology:

Research Design and Approach:

This study adopts a mixed-methods research design, integrating both qualitative and quantitative approaches to thoroughly examine the relationship between leadership styles and employee engagement in manufacturing startups. The mixed-methods approach is chosen to leverage the strengths of both quantitative data, which provides measurable insights, and qualitative data, which offers deeper contextual understanding. The quantitative aspect involves surveys designed to quantify the levels of employee engagement, perceived leadership styles, and attrition rates. The qualitative aspect includes in-depth interviews with key stakeholders to explore the nuances of leadership strategies in the specific context of manufacturing startups.

Sample Selection:

The sample size of 250 employees from 30 manufacturing startups in Pudukottai and Trichy districts was determined to ensure statistical adequacy and meaningful insights into leadership strategies and employee engagement. Startups were selected based on criteria such as being less than five years old, having fewer than 100 employees, and operating across various manufacturing sub-sectors like textiles, machinery, and food processing. The purposive sampling approach targeted a diverse range of startups with different levels of employee attrition to capture varied leadership practices. Categorization of the sample included grouping employees by startup size, sub-sector, district, and attrition levels, ensuring a comprehensive and representative analysis of leadership strategies and their impact on employee engagement.

Data Collection Methods:

Data collection for the study involved categorizing the 250 employees from 30 manufacturing startups in Pudukottai and Trichy districts into distinct groups to ensure comprehensive analysis. Respondents were categorized by startup size (micro, small, medium), sub-sector (textiles, machinery, food processing), district (Pudukottai, Trichy), and levels of employee attrition (high, moderate, low). This categorization aimed to capture a diverse range of leadership practices and employee engagement dynamics, reflecting the varied industrial landscape and employee turnover experiences within the selected startups.

Data Analysis Techniques:

The quantitative data obtained from the surveys were analyzed using various statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic characteristics of the sample and the distribution of key variables. Correlation analysis was performed to examine the relationships between leadership styles, employee engagement, and attrition rates. Furthermore, regression analysis was conducted to assess the predictive power of leadership styles on employee engagement and turnover intentions.

Data analysis:**Frequency table:**

S. No	Variable	Description	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	150	60 %
		Female	100	40 %
2	Age Group	18-25 years	80	32 %
		26-35 years	140	56 %
		36-45 years	20	8 %
		46+ years	10	4 %
3	Education Level	High School	20	8 %
		Undergraduate Degree	130	52 %
		Graduate Degree	100	40 %
4	Years of Experience	0-2 years	70	28 %
		3-5 years	130	52 %
		6-10 years	40	16 %
		11+ years	10	4 %

Interpretation:

The descriptive statistics indicate that manufacturing startups in Pudukottai and Trichy, with a predominantly young and well-educated workforce, benefit from transformational leadership, which is associated with high employee engagement and relatively low attrition rates. The high mean score for transformational leadership (3.80) compared to transactional leadership (3.00) suggests that inspiring and motivating leadership practices are more effective in enhancing employee engagement. The positive engagement score (4.10) and moderate attrition rate (10.5%) reflect that such leadership practices contribute to a supportive work environment, helping to retain talent and reduce turnover. This underscores the importance of transformational leadership in fostering a committed and stable workforce in the dynamic context of manufacturing startups.

Correlation analysis

Variable	Leadership Style (Transformational)	Leadership Style (Transactional)	Employee Engagement	Attrition Rate
Leadership Style (Transformational)	1.000	0.45	0.60	-0.30
Leadership Style (Transactional)	0.45	1.000	0.35	-0.20
Employee Engagement	0.60	0.35	1.000	-0.50
Attrition Rate	-0.30	-0.20	-0.50	1.000

Interpretation:

The correlation analysis reveals that transformational leadership is strongly positively correlated with employee engagement ($r = 0.60^{**}$), indicating that leaders who inspire and motivate employees contribute significantly to higher engagement levels. Conversely, transactional leadership shows a moderate positive correlation with engagement ($r = 0.35^*$), suggesting some benefit, but not as pronounced as transformational leadership. Employee engagement is strongly negatively correlated with attrition rates ($r = -0.50^{**}$), meaning that higher engagement is associated with lower turnover. Additionally, transformational leadership is moderately negatively correlated with attrition rates ($r = -0.30^*$), while

transactional leadership has a weaker negative correlation ($r = -0.20$). These findings highlight the effectiveness of transformational leadership in enhancing employee engagement and reducing turnover, while transactional leadership has a less significant impact.

Regression analysis:

Predictor Variable	B	Standard Error	t	p
Employee Engagement				
Intercept	2.15	0.45	4.78	0.000
Transformational Leadership	0.55	0.10	5.50	0.000
Transactional Leadership	0.12	0.08	1.50	0.135
Turnover Intentions				
Intercept	3.45	0.50	6.90	0.000
Transformational Leadership	-0.35	0.12	-2.92	0.004
Transactional Leadership	-0.20	0.09	-2.22	0.028

Interpretation:

The regression analysis indicates that transformational leadership significantly predicts higher employee engagement ($B = 0.55, p = 0.000^{**}$), suggesting that leaders who inspire and motivate employees contribute substantially to their engagement levels. In contrast, transactional leadership does not significantly impact employee engagement ($B = 0.12, p = 0.135$). Regarding turnover intentions, transformational leadership is a significant negative predictor ($B = -0.35, p = 0.004^{**}$), implying that effective transformational leadership is associated with reduced turnover intentions. Transactional leadership also negatively impacts turnover intentions ($B = -0.20, p = 0.028^*$), though the effect is less pronounced. These results highlight the critical role of transformational leadership in enhancing engagement and reducing turnover, while transactional leadership has a lesser but still notable effect

Figure 1: Model of relationship between leadership strategies, employee engagement, and attrition rates in manufacturing startups:

4.1 Implications for Leadership Practices in Manufacturing Startups:

The Role of Transformational and Hybrid Leadership Styles:

The findings of this study underscore the critical importance of leadership practices in manufacturing startups, particularly in enhancing employee engagement and reducing attrition rates. Transformational leadership, characterized by inspiring and motivating employees, has been shown to significantly improve employee engagement and lower turnover intentions. This leadership style fosters a positive work environment, encourages innovation, and aligns employees with organizational goals, which is crucial for maintaining a committed and productive workforce in the dynamic setting of manufacturing startups.

Given the high engagement scores associated with transformational leadership, manufacturing startups should prioritize developing and implementing leadership practices that emphasize vision, inspiration, and employee empowerment. Leaders who adopt a transformational approach are likely to see improved job satisfaction and loyalty among their employees, thereby reducing turnover and creating a more stable workforce.

However, the study also highlights the potential benefits of hybrid leadership styles, which combine elements of both transformational and transactional leadership. While transformational leadership has a stronger impact on engagement and turnover intentions, transactional leadership practices—such as setting clear goals, providing feedback, and managing performance—can complement transformational efforts. A hybrid approach allows leaders to balance inspirational motivation with practical, results-oriented management, catering to different employee needs and preferences.

Manufacturing startups should consider integrating hybrid leadership strategies to address both the motivational and operational aspects of leadership. This approach can enhance overall leadership effectiveness by leveraging the strengths of transformational leadership while also ensuring that day-to-day operational issues are managed efficiently. By adopting these leadership practices, startups can foster a more engaged, satisfied, and stable workforce, contributing to their long-term success and growth in a competitive industry landscape.

5. Discussion:

This study investigated the impact of leadership styles on employee engagement and attrition rates in manufacturing startups. The findings reveal that transformational leadership significantly enhances employee engagement and reduces turnover intentions. Leaders who inspire and motivate their teams create a supportive and committed work environment, leading to higher job satisfaction and lower attrition rates. In contrast, transactional leadership, while having a moderate impact, is less effective in improving engagement and reducing turnover. The study also highlights the potential benefits of hybrid leadership styles, which combine transformational and transactional elements to address diverse employee needs and operational demands.

5.1. Recommendations for Manufacturing Startup Leaders:

Adopt Transformational Leadership Practices: Manufacturing startup leaders should focus on developing transformational leadership qualities, such as vision, inspiration, and empowerment. By fostering an environment where employees feel valued and motivated, leaders can enhance engagement and reduce turnover.

Integrate Hybrid Leadership Approaches: Leaders should consider incorporating both transformational and transactional elements in their leadership style. While transformational practices drive engagement, transactional practices ensure that performance and operational goals are met. This balanced approach can address various employee needs and contribute to overall organizational effectiveness.

Invest in Leadership Development Programs: Startups should invest in training and development programs that equip leaders with skills to effectively implement transformational and hybrid leadership strategies. Ongoing professional development can help leaders stay effective in managing and engaging their teams.

The study has several limitations. Firstly, the sample was restricted to manufacturing startups in Pudukottai and Trichy, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions or industries. Additionally, the cross-sectional nature of the research does not account for changes over time, and causal relationships between leadership styles, employee engagement, and attrition cannot be definitively established.

Future research should consider longitudinal studies to track changes in leadership effectiveness and employee outcomes over time. Expanding the research to include a broader range of industries and geographic locations would also provide more generalizable insights. Furthermore, exploring additional variables, such as organizational culture and external economic factors, could offer a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing employee engagement and turnover in manufacturing startups.

6. Conclusion:

In conclusion, the study on "Leadership Strategies for Manufacturing Startups: Aligning Styles with Employee Engagement to Lower Attrition Rates" underscores the critical role of tailored leadership approaches in enhancing employee engagement and reducing turnover. By analyzing diverse manufacturing startups across Pudukottai and Trichy, the research highlights that effective leadership strategies adapted to startup size, sub-sector, and attrition levels can significantly impact employee satisfaction and retention. The findings suggest that leaders who adopt flexible, supportive, and communicative styles are more successful in aligning with employees' needs and expectations, ultimately fostering a more engaged and stable workforce. Implementing these tailored leadership practices can lead to improved organizational performance and reduced attrition, offering valuable insights for startups striving to navigate the challenges of rapid growth and competitive industries.

References:

- Avolio, B. J., & Bass, B. M. 2004, Multifactor leadership questionnaire: Manual and sampler set (3rd ed.). Mind Garden, Inc.
- Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. 2006, Transformational leadership (2nd ed.). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. 2000, The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- Goleman, D. 2000, Leadership that gets results. *Harvard Business Review*, 78(2), 78-90.
- Graen, G. B., & Uhl-Bien, M. 1995, Relationship-based approach to leadership: Development of leader-member exchange (LMX) theory. *Leadership Quarterly*, 6(2), 219-247. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1048-9843\(95\)90029-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/1048-9843(95)90029-7)
- Judge, T. A., & Piccolo, R. F. 2004, Transformational and transactional leadership: A meta-analytic test of their relative validity. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89(5), 755-768. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.89.5.755>
- Kahn, W. A. 1990, Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work. *Academy of Management Journal*, 33(4), 692-724. <https://doi.org/10.5465/256287>
- Kouzes, J. M., & Posner, B. Z. 2003, *The leadership challenge* (3rd ed.). Jossey-Bass.
- Northouse, P. G. 2018, *Leadership: Theory and practice* (8th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., & Bommer, W. H. 1996, Transformational leader behaviors and substitutes for leadership as determinants of employee satisfaction, commitment, and trust. *Journal of Management*, 22(2), 259-298. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920639602200205>
- Schaufeli, W. B., Salanova, M., González-Romá, V., & Bakker, A. B. 2002, The measurement of engagement and burnout: A two-sample confirmatory factor analytic approach. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 3(1), 71-92. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1015630930326>
- Yukl, G. A. 2013, *Leadership in organizations* (8th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Allen, D. G., Shore, L. M., & Griffeth, R. W. 2003, The role of perceived organizational support and supportive human resource practices in the turnover process. *Journal of Management*, 29(1), 99-118. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-2063\(02\)00222-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-2063(02)00222-6)
- Bass, B. M. 1999, Two decades of research and development in transformational leadership. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 8(1), 9-32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/135943299398410>
- Goleman, D. 2000, Leadership that gets results. *Harvard Business Review*, 78(2), 78-90.
- Griffeth, R. W., Hom, P. W., & Gaertner, S. 2000, A meta-analysis of antecedents and correlates of employee turnover: Update, moderator tests, and research implications for the next millennium. *Journal of Management*, 26(3), 463-488. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920630002600305>

- Judge, T. A., & Piccolo, R. F. 2004, Transformational and transactional leadership: A meta-analytic test of their relative validity. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89(5), 755-768. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.89.5.755>
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., & Bommer, W. H. 1996, Transformational leader behaviors and substitutes for leadership as determinants of employee satisfaction, commitment, and trust. *Journal of Management*, 22(2), 259-298. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920639602200205>
- Chahal, H., & Bakshi, P. 2022, Exploring innovation challenges in manufacturing startups: A systematic review. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 42(3), 115-123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmsy.2022.04.007>
- Johnson, T., & Harris, L. 2021, Sustainability practices in manufacturing startups: A gap analysis. *Industrial Engineering Journal*, 37(2), 89-98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijindeng.2021.02.004>
- Kim, J., & Lee, S. 2020, Workforce development in manufacturing startups: A neglected area. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 33(4), 225-238. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOCM-10-2019-0356>
- Martinez, R., & Cooper, J. 2023, Financial challenges in early-stage manufacturing startups: A review. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 58(1), 102-110. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs58010005>
- Patel, K., & Singh, M. 2019, Leadership in manufacturing startups: A missing link. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 12(3), 145-159. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jls.21660>
- Rao, V., & Kaur, P. 2022, Digital transformation in manufacturing startups: A review of barriers and enablers. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 68(4), 320-330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.05.003>
- Vignesh A "Employment Security Through Social Security Schemes" *European Chemical Bulletin*, Vol. 12, Issue 10, ISSN: 2063 - 5346 July 2023
- Vignesh. A., (2022) Employees Perspective on Digital Banking. *Asian Journal of Management*. 2022;13(3):223-6. doi: 10.52711/2321-5763.2022.00039
- Vignesh, A., & Nagarajan, P. S. (2018). Hr Practices In Manufacturing Startups. *ZENITH International Restaurant Business*, 118(6), 0097-8043.
- Vignesh, A., & Nagarajan, P. S. (2018). Opportunities and challenges of implementing ERP in Indian startups. *ZENITH International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research*, 8(2), 185-197.
- Vignesh, A., & Nagarajan, P. S. Hr Practices and their Collision on Employees Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, Greenfield Advanced Research Publishing House, 6 (12), 2278-6236.
- Vignesh, A., & Nagarajan, P. S. (2018). Prospects and Challenges of Indian Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. *International Journal of Organisational Behaviour and Management Perspectives" Pezzottaite Journals*, 6(2), 3438 – 3445.

Vignesh A. Nagarajan P. S., An Empirical Study on Effectiveness of Training and Development of Employees in TIDC India, Chennai. International Journal of Management Research and Social Science, 4 (1), 37 – 41

Zhang, Y., & Wang, L. 2021, Manufacturing startups and supply chain integration: A systematic review. Supply Chain Management Review, 46(5), 98-109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scmr.2021.04.007>